

Report for Funders
based on the SEA-EU Workshop 2025

**Open Science Capacity Building:
Finding solutions**

Report for Funders

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Executive summary

This report is based on the GATE-SEA-EU workshop in Hamburg and on the published workshop report by Priess-Buchheit et al. (2026). It is written for readers who may not yet be familiar with either GATE or the SEA-EU collaboration. Its purpose is to explain why the workshop mattered for research funders and what practical lessons emerged for future Open Science support.

The workshop brought together two representatives of national funders from two different European contexts out of the 27 countries in Europe: Croatia, as a widening country, and Germany, as a non-widening country. Together with SEA-EU Open Science ambassadors from Kiel University, the University of Split, and the University of Malta, as well as GATE contributors and external Open Science and legal experts, they brought strategically important national funding perspectives into the discussion (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). Their voices mattered because they helped test whether the ideas developed in the workshop were meaningful not only at the institutional level, but also from the perspective of national funding policy and implementation. The aim was to examine how Open Science capacity building can be strengthened through better alignment between funding frameworks, institutional practice, and emerging developments at the intersection of Open Science and artificial intelligence.

A central message emerged very clearly: Open Science capacity building succeeds when training, infrastructures, evaluation systems, and incentives are aligned (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). Across the workshop discussions, common needs included stronger coordination, sustainable infrastructures, legal clarity, recognition of Open Science contributions, and better support for responsible AI use in research workflows.

GATE contributed a structured evidence base on Open Science guiding thoughts, current practices, and developments at the Open Science-AI intersection (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). On this basis, participants developed five concrete action areas for funders:

- awareness and training
- policy and evaluation alignment
- responsible AI integration
- legal and structural support
- collaborative Lighthouse Projects

This report highlights aspects that are especially relevant for funders and that still need stronger operational support. These include embedding Open Science directly into funding instruments, supporting Lighthouse Projects as strategic pilots, investing in metaresearch and funding transparency, and helping shape trustworthy AI practices in research ecosystems.

Funders responded positively to both the Lighthouse Projects concept and GATE's evidence-based approach (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). The discussion showed that funders often need clearer insight into how openness is implemented in practice. For that reason, GATE

is relevant not only as a source of information, but also as a collaborative and trustworthy non-profit mechanism for connecting evidence, stakeholders, and solution-oriented dialogue.

1. Introduction

For research funders, Open Science is no longer only a policy commitment. It is also a strategic lever to improve research quality, efficiency, transparency, and societal impact. Yet the workshop confirmed that implementation remains uneven because processes are not always aligned with Open Science principles (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). This report therefore shows where funders can move from general support for Open Science to more concrete action through funding instruments, evaluation reform, infrastructure investment, and support for metaresearch.

The report is grounded in the GATE-SEA-EU workshop held in Hamburg in October 2025. The workshop was designed as a two-day collaboration to strengthen Open Science capacity across SEA-EU partners and countries, especially where Open Science meets new possibilities and challenges such as AI. It was intended to turn shared evidence into practical action and to use one hybrid funder session to test and refine ideas with national funding organisations from the SEA EU countries.

What makes this workshop especially relevant for funders is that it connected real institutional challenges with actionable funding implications. It was not only a discussion about principles. It was designed to support the development of a SEA-EU Open Science Capacity-Building Roadmap and to discuss how funders could validate, strengthen, and support this work. The workshop brief explicitly framed the funders' roundtable as an opportunity to align funding policies, instruments, and support mechanisms with documented capacity-building needs across the alliance.

1.1 What is SEA-EU?

SEA-EU is a European university alliance that brings together coastal universities across Europe in order to strengthen collaboration in research, education, and societal engagement. In the workshop materials, SEA-EU is described as a "European Coastal Campus" that supports joint study programmes, mobility, seed funding for collaborative research, and cooperation across institutions and countries. In the context of this report, SEA-EU matters because it provides a transnational framework in which Open Science capacity building can be developed jointly rather than separately at each institution.

1.2 What is GATE?

GATE, the Open Science Learning GATE, is a non-profit initiative that supports Open Science capacity building by connecting communities and continuously informing stakeholders about evolving practices, services, and guiding thoughts, including developments at the intersection of

Open Science and AI. GATE is a community-driven infrastructure that gathers evidence from Open Science practitioners and turns this evidence into actionable insights through the GATE Service and the annual GATE Report.

In simple terms, GATE works in two connected steps:

- **GATE Service:** a structured community collection point where Open Science knowledge creators such as trainers, educators, and authors describe the guiding thoughts embedded in their materials and practices. This creates a growing qualitative evidence base.
- **GATE Report:** the research team evaluates and synthesises the collected inputs and shares the results in reports that can support quality-oriented capacity building across the research ecosystem.

Background: How GATE supports funders and the research ecosystem

GATE is a non-profit initiative emphasising the deep interconnection of OS and AI. As highlighted in the published SEA-EU workshop report, GATE systematically maps Open Science guiding thoughts and their development over time, creating an evidence base for decision-making across the research ecosystem (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026).

This role is reinforced by the GATE Engagement Feedback 1 publication, which shows that GATE was designed from the outset as a community-facing and stakeholder-oriented initiative, including explicit support for research funders (Miller et al., 2025). The engagement feedback identified five groups for whom GATE offers concrete value: trainers, research communities, policy makers, research funding organisations, and data infrastructures (Miller et al., 2025). In particular, the publication highlights that Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) can use the GATE as a valuable resource for gathering the information necessary to enforce standards for funding applications. It can serve as a reference or 'gold-standard' guide for implementing Open Science in research projects, ensuring compliance and facilitating better funding practices (Miller et al., 2025).

For funders, this makes GATE a valuable collaboration partner. Funding decisions often rely on assumptions about how openness is understood and implemented in practice. GATE reduces this uncertainty by offering structured, community-driven insights that connect

researchers, trainers, infrastructures, funders, publishers, and policy makers. In this way, GATE represents one trustworthy solution that can support funders in designing evidence-informed strategies that foster transparency, reproducibility, and responsible innovation for the future benefit of society.

The engagement feedback also underlines an important systemic point: GATE does not only collect knowledge, it helps build a dynamic ecosystem in which stakeholders can connect, collaborate, build capacity, and advance knowledge in Open Science (Miller et al., 2025). Seen in this light, the workshop in Hamburg can be understood as one of the concrete engagement activities through which GATE began putting this support for funders into practice. This is particularly relevant for funders that want to support long-term coordination rather than isolated interventions.

GATE systematically collects and analyses community-based knowledge on OS guiding thoughts - the evolving concepts that underpin reliable OS practice. By mapping these developments over time, GATE provides an evidence base (via the annual [GATE Reports](#)) that enables researchers, educators, institutions, (data-) infrastructures, funders and policymakers to engage in informed, constructive dialogue on how to implement OS effectively and responsibly.

1.3 Why the workshop results matter for national funders in University Alliance contexts

The workshop materials make clear that the event was intentionally designed to include national funders from SEA EU countries. Participants first worked through institutional perspectives, GATE evidence, thematic discussions, and guided co-design. The workshop then culminated in a hybrid dialogue with national funders in order to validate emerging ideas and explore how policy and support mechanisms could enable enduring cross-national capacity building.

This is important because these funders were not invited only as observers. The workshop background documents explicitly presented the funders' roundtable as a milestone in GATE's broader engagement with funding organisations and as a way to shape the alliance roadmap with direct input from the funding perspective. Seen in this light, the workshop in Hamburg was one of the planned activities through which GATE began to put its support for funders into practice. The participation of one funder from a widening country and one from a non-widening country gave the discussion particular value, because it brought together perspectives shaped by different national funding environments within Europe and made the exchange more meaningful for future cross-national learning.

2. Alignment with national funders from Europe

This chapter highlights the priorities, expectations, and implications that are especially relevant for Open Science from a funding perspective.

2.1 Shared priorities and perspectives

Workshop participants converged around several common priorities. Open Science should strengthen research quality rather than become a bureaucratic objective. Infrastructures should enable openness from the outset. Responsible AI and knowledge security require growing attention. Researcher-driven approaches are more likely to succeed than purely prescriptive ones.

The representative from Croatian Science Foundation, speaking from the perspective of a widening country, noted strong alignment between the proposed capacity-building direction and Croatia's national Open Science plan, including open access, transparent assessment of project outputs, and links to EOSC-related developments. This supports the view that European University Alliance activities can complement national strategies when they are grounded in practical needs and realistic implementation pathways.

The need for evidence based support is strengthened by [Miller et al., 2025](#), which explicitly identifies research funding organisations as one of GATE's core stakeholder groups and makes clear that GATE planned from the beginning to support funders. It describes the GATE as a resource that can help RFOs enforce standards for funding applications, serve as a reference, and facilitate better funding practices. The same publication also places funders within a wider stakeholder ecosystem, showing how GATE can help connect funding practice with trainers, research communities, policy makers, and data infrastructures.

The DFG perspective, representing a non-widening country context, stressed that Open Science should serve research quality and scientific robustness. It also highlighted the importance of knowledge security, transparency in AI models and data provenance, and scientific autonomy from large commercial platforms.

Both funders responded positively to the evidence-based role of GATE in the workshop. The discussion showed that funders often need clearer insight into how openness is implemented in everyday research practice. In this context, GATE was recognised as valuable because it provides a structured, community-connected evidence base that can inform policy reflection, capacity building, and future collaboration.

2.3 What national funders might support next

The following suggestions emerged from the workshop discussions:

- integrate Open Science more directly into funding calls and assessment criteria
- support Lighthouse Projects as strategic funding instruments
- invest in metaresearch as a core area of funding practice and in designated calls
- increase transparency of funding landscapes and collaboration structures
- use evidence- and stakeholder-informed reference points to improve funding standards, identify community needs, and reduce duplication across the Open Science landscape

3. GATE-informed action areas for funders

The workshop presented five action areas for funders. In the workshop process, these action areas were not abstract themes; they emerged from the joint interpretation of institutional experiences, GATE evidence, expert input, and funder dialogue. The sections below explain these five action areas in a way that is accessible to readers who did not attend the workshop.

3.1 Awareness and training

Participants emphasised the need to strengthen Open Science and AI literacy across researchers, educators, administrators, evaluators, and funding actors (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). Awareness is a precondition for systemic change, but it must be backed by visible examples, stable communication structures, and training opportunities that address real needs.

For funders, this means supporting training infrastructures and exchange formats that connect institutions, researchers, and funders, as well as recognising the value of community-based knowledge exchange on current Open Science developments.

3.2 Policy and evaluation alignment

The workshop highlighted the need for Open Science to be embedded in evaluation systems rather than treated as an optional add-on (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). This includes recognising shared research artefacts, transparent workflows, and open outputs in funding, recognition, and promotion contexts.

For funders, this means embedding Open Science criteria into proposal evaluation, reporting, and impact assessment, rewarding Open Science practices beyond traditional publication metrics, and helping to harmonise institutional and funder expectations even where national systems differ.

3.3 Responsible AI integration

Given the growing role of AI in research and administration, participants called for coordinated guidance on transparency, provenance, accountability, and knowledge security (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). This applies both to researchers using AI and to funders considering AI-supported workflows in assessment or administration.

For funders, this means defining expectations for responsible and transparent AI use in funded projects, supporting secure infrastructures and internal systems where sensitive data or assessment processes are involved, and connecting AI guidance to Open Science principles such as traceability, interpretability, and accountability.

3.4 Legal and structural support

Open Science capacity building depends on more than goodwill (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). It requires infrastructures, legal clarity, and organisational coherence. Participants highlighted licensing, intellectual property, repository interoperability, and reproducibility support as areas where clearer structures are needed.

For funders, this means supporting open and interoperable infrastructures, providing clarity or coordinated guidance on licensing, rights, and data governance, and investing in reproducibility and metaresearch mechanisms that identify systemic weaknesses and opportunities for improvement.

3.5 Lighthouse Projects

A central outcome of the workshop was the proposal to advance Lighthouse Projects: visible, collaborative pilots that demonstrate Open Science in practice (Priess-Buchheit et al., 2026). These are researcher-driven projects designed to make openness tangible, scalable, and useful across institutions and countries.

Participants were not only discussing policy at a high level; they were also asked to co-design practical measures, pilots, and roadmap elements that could be implemented across institutions. Lighthouse Projects are therefore best understood as practical demonstration projects that make Open Science visible through concrete examples.

Lighthouse Projects will

- demonstrate OS in practice through tangible, visible, and collaborative projects, serving as scalable, translatable exemplars (“lighthouses”) of OS best practices within and across the SEA-EU Alliance universities.
- show how openness improves research quality, reproducibility and reveal impact of (proactive and retro-active) OS practices (quality, reproducibility, collaboration, societal impact) in the European R&I landscape.
- enhance cross-national and cross-community (researchers, institutions, funders, educators) collaboration and (policy) learning beyond projects.
- Reduce (funding) waste and maximise research quality, reliability, and trust through open sharing.
- exemplify OS as a mechanism and enabling stakeholders articulate their own motivation (definition of goals) to do their action.

For national funders, Lighthouse Projects are especially attractive because they focus on practice rather than abstract compliance. They allow experimentation, learning, and evidence generation without creating the impression of a purely top-down policy imposition.

4. Next steps and conclusion

4.1 Next steps

The next steps emerging from this funder-focused report follow logically from the funder dialogue and the action areas above:

- support the development of Lighthouse Projects as funded pilots for coordinated Open Science implementation
- refine the funding-relevant aspects of the SEA-EU roadmap
- integrate outcomes into the GATE report cycle so they inform the wider research ecosystem
- expand engagement with national and European funders

4.2 Conclusion

Building on the GATE-SEA-EU workshop, this report highlights that Open Science capacity building depends on funder action.

Activities such as the Hamburg workshop provide a transparent, reliable, and cooperative mechanism to support this shift by connecting evidence, community input, and solution-oriented dialogue. In that sense, the workshop was not an isolated meeting. It was part of a broader process through which GATE and SEA-EU worked together to translate evidence into practical capacity-building strategies and to test these strategies with funders.

With targeted support from funders, the SEA-EU roadmap and Lighthouse Projects can evolve into scalable, evidence-based instruments for Open Science implementation across Europe.

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The GATE initiative, as a cooperative, transparent, and non-profit effort, continues to establish itself as a trustworthy solution to build and maintain Open Science capacities. For more information or to join the GATE service, visit www.openscienceGATE.com.